

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Learning Sound Representations Using Triplet-loss

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Abstract

Sound representations play an important role in audio information retrieval. Good representations effectively reduce the data size of audio recordings while keeping the acoustic and/or semantic characteristics. Recent studies have demonstrated that machine learning approaches which rely on large sound collections successfully learn such representations. However, these approaches come with a few drawbacks such as the complexity of building a taxonomy, the cost of sound annotation, and the difficulty to utilize multi-labelled annotation.

In this work, we aim to address the issues by a similarity learning framework. We employ triplet loss in which our sound representations are optimized directly using a distance measure. This allows for more effective use of user-made and multi-labelled sound descriptions from online sound collections and removes the need for a taxonomy. Furthermore, by adjusting the triplet loss with a natural language processing technique, we investigate the benefit of word representations of sound descriptions to make our sound representations semantically rich.

Experimental results revealed that the sound representations we learned in similarity learning achieved the performance almost equal to the state-of-the-art model in a clustering task, even when we used a limited amount of training data. On the other hand, we also found a few drawbacks of our learning strategy such as the poor performance in a discriminative task.

Our code for this project is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/kokimame/OpenFSE>

An additional tool to visualize audio representations with audio-playing feature is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/kokimame/tensoba>

Keywords: Sound representation, Similarity learning, Triplet loss

Chapter 1

Introduction

Information retrieval is a key human activity that has a decisive role in shaping our society. With the emergence of agriculture around 10,000 years ago, people in a hunting-gathering lifestyle had first ever had a demand for storing and retrieving information [1] such as weather to maximize their crops in the future. Since then, the importance of information retrieval has only magnified as our society became more complex. Over the course of history, we saw many breakthroughs that radically changed how human exchanges information, such as Cuneiform, the first writing system developed by the Sumerian in 3200 BC, and the Gutenberg's printing system which succeeded in automating the production of books.

Today, the internet provides us with the capacity to store an infinite amount of information. As such, the amount of online data keeps growing exponentially. According to the IBM Marketing Cloud study [2], 90% of this data on the internet has been created since 2016. For instance, users on YouTube upload 500 hours of new video each minute of every day, and Instagram users upload over 100 million photos and videos every day. The internet is bidirectional; users are not only consumers of the data but producers who equally contribute to this data growth.

From a technical perspective, the increase of the online data was only possible after a multitude of advancements which started from the late 20th century in the area of processors, computer memory, computer storage, and computer networks. As the

data quantity increased, the quality of the data had also diversified. In the earliest days, the internet was almost entirely text-based. However, with more powerful computers and the invention of efficient coding of data, such as MP3 for digital audio and MP4 for videos, a wider variety of media became available online.

Accompanied by the growth in data quantity and quality, the science of retrieving digital data (Information Retrieval, IR) had thrived. In its earliest form, an IR system takes a user query and finds relevant information from large text databases. This basic workflow has not changed yet. However, IR systems today search for not only text but multimedia content stored in even larger resources. The most popular application of this is web search engines that search the World Wide Web for a mix of information, including web pages (texts), videos, audio, and other types of medium.

Compared with text, multimedia resources which include audio, image, and video, are naturally large in size and maybe noisy and redundant [3]. Therefore, for online multimedia content, automatic methods to summarize the content into a smaller set of essences (representation) is important for effective retrieval and organization. The essences that embody the characteristics of the original data are called *features*.

Extracting features from media content traditionally requires considerable effort and domain-knowledge. For example, mel-frequency cepstrum (MFCCs) is a popular feature extracted in sound processing. It is popular due to its advantage of less complexity in implementation. But even so, it still requires careful consideration for audio signal processing, such as framing, windowing, and Fourier transform.

Recently, the advancements in deep learning have shown that neural networks can replace laborious feature engineering with automated feature learning. Unlike features like MFCC which serve general purposes, deep learning approaches can produce features for a much more specific purpose. In the context of this research, for example, we aim to produce sound representations that are specifically designed for automatic organization and retrieval of online sound data.

While deep learning has seen growing popularity and success, it comes with several

drawbacks. For example, it usually requires a large collection of data that are annotated with a predefined set of vocabulary (taxonomy). Due to the large scale of the data, the cost of data annotation, and the complexity of building a taxonomy often becomes a limiting factor that prohibits well-generalized features. Moreover, the representations based on popular approaches systematically fail to capture the similarity relationship of the input which should play an important role in data clustering.

We are interested in an automatic organization of sound data in which two audio recordings similar in some sense are projected closely and otherwise far away. In this work, we will achieve this by using a similarity learning strategy. Similarity learning is also a method of deep learning but it can learn the similarity relationship of input data.

More specifically, our sound representations are optimized with a triplet loss function. We design and evaluate a variation of the triplet loss. Our loss function allows for more effective use of user-made and multi-labeled audio descriptions from online sound collections and removes the need for a taxonomy. Furthermore, the loss function employs a natural language processing technique to embrace more semantic content in the sound representations.

Finally, we compare the quality of our sound representations with two baseline models in both objective and subjective evaluation. To evaluate objectively, we set up two tasks; one discriminative (classification) task and one clustering task. For the subjective evaluation, we use a visualization tool that allows users to interact with clustering of sound representations intuitively.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

This chapter reviews the long-running technological advances from the past, making readers certain of the state-of-the-art studies in audio information retrieval. Since we aim to learn fine sound representations for automatic organization and retrieval of online sound data, we think of two independent issues: the way of representing sounds (production of audio features) and the way of presenting sounds based on the given representation (clustering approach).

The rest of this chapter is organized as follows: in the next section, we discuss the most general topic of our research: information retrieval, focusing on its connection to sound and music computing. Then, in Section 2, a class of hand-crafted audio features is introduced. In Section 3, we cover the audio features that are recently developed with the help of deep learning. Among those new kinds of features, we focus on those learned from similarity learning and discuss its practical use for clustering and classification in Section 4. In Section 5, a review of clustering methods is presented with the focus on two topics, the partitional clustering and Rand Index.

2.1 Information Retrieval and Audio

The purpose of this section is to emphasize that our work lies at an intersection of information retrieval (IR) and audio engineering problems. We introduce fun-

damental technologies that are essential to modern IR processes such as database technologies.

2.1.1 Information Retrieval

Information retrieval is the science of finding information that satisfies an information need from a large collection of those resources [4]. Most IR systems start by taking as input a text, a search query that describes a user's information need. Then, given a query, the system ranks the data objects which are represented by information in the database. The rank of relevance between the query and each object is measured using a numeric score on how well the object matches with the query [5]. Finally, it shows the top-ranking objects to the user.

While traditionally IR is used to mean searching for textual information from a collection of other texts [4], IR is becoming the dominant form of any kind of information access. Today, the objects that IR systems deal with are not only texts but a wide variety of multimedia data are also supported such as images [6] and sound [7], and the retrieval process can be performed using either a full-text query or content-based query [8].

Techniques and algorithms which enable efficient retrieval process vary with the kind of information to search for. For example, Music Information Retrieval (MIR), which is a branch of IR and relevant to our work, focuses on retrieving information from music.

2.1.2 Database System

Database system is one of the underlying technologies in IR. A database in a computer system stores a mix of structured data, ranging from credential files to multimedia contents. It is an integral part of many web-based applications [9] and makes possible a satisfying IR experience on the internet. Most databases rely on structured query language (SQL) in order to retrieve its data.

However, searching in a database itself is not considered as IR because it lacks the

ranking process of the search results [10]. This means an IR system returns the results which may or may not match the query in the order of relevance. On the other hand, a database system typically returns nothing when no matching object is available in its data collection. Furthermore, an IR system does not limit the user to a specific query language while such languages like SQL or MongoDB are commonly used in database systems [11].

Freesound¹ is a non-profit website that hosts a collaborative web-based repository of Creative Commons Licensed sounds. It has been maintained at the Music Technology Group (MTG) in Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona. The repository was launched in 2005 with an initial goal to provide a large royalty-free sound database to sound researchers for testing their algorithms [12]. Since then, it has been widely adopted by sound artists, application developers, and all sorts of content creators and became a standard website for sharing sounds under the Creative Commons License².

Figure 1 shows the system architecture of Freesound. The users search and retrieve audio recordings through an interactive interface on a web browser. What's often left invisible and unknown to the public is a large number of server-side processes running in the back end. As for Freesound, critical processes are running in the backend to automatically organize and retrieve audio recordings. We look more closely in the following sections, such as similarity search and feature extractions.

Figure 1: Overview of system architecture of Freesound [12].

¹<https://freesound.org/>

²<https://creativecommons.org/>

2.2 Audio Features

Humans are naturally good at audio retrieval. We are born with a set of abilities to discriminate against a wide range of sounds. Moreover, we can relate and match similar sounds [13]. We also have the capability to detect and relate sound events or “acoustic objects” which we have never encountered before, based on how that phenomenon stands out against its background [14].

However, building such abilities in computers is very difficult. Raw audio recordings are essentially a featureless collection of bytes with most rudimentary information embedded such as file name, format, and sampling rate. To make computers understand sounds more effectively, we first need to transform sounds into a small set of essences (features). In the section, we review various approaches to extract features from audio recordings.

2.2.1 Feature

In machine learning, a feature is most briefly defined as an individual measurable property or characteristic of a phenomenon being observed [15]. Features that we use in this work are always real-valued numeric while they may vary in different contexts such as categorical (e.g., musical note); ordinal (e.g., "*mf*", "*f*" or "*ff*" for music dynamics).

In the case of image retrieval systems, IR systems traditionally relied on manually-created textual annotations to measure the relevance between user’s query and information in resources (keyword annotation paradigm) [16]. With the rise of the amount of data that must be processed, the annotation approach had to be complemented with faster and automatic feature extraction. In image retrieval, researchers found that the use of low-level visual features such as shapes and colors can be superior to the traditional annotation-based approach in terms of robustness because automation removed the human subjectivity [17]. Furthermore, features are used to map from a large, complex data to a lower dimension to facilitate searches [18].

Audio features are a crucial component of our work. In most of the audio retrieval applications, audio features are obtained in a pre-processing step, called feature extraction [19]. In this context, feature extraction is a process that converts the raw audio waveform (time series data) into a set of numerical vector representations.

This section aims to offer a review of two general classes of audio features, acoustic features, and symbolic features, that researchers and developers commonly find useful for a range of audio applications. Audio features discussed in this section are crafted in traditional approaches. Some are based on low-level features such as fundamental frequency and harmonicity of signals and others are high-level features that are designed to provide semanticity of sounds.

2.2.2 Acoustic Features

Pitch, loudness, and timbre are the acoustic features that are traditionally used to describe sounds and commonly adapted in many audio retrieval applications [20, 21, 22]. Those features are closely related to our audio perception and sensory stimuli we receive when we hear sounds. Interested readers are referred to [23, 24] to find complete coverage of audio features and their effects on perception. Acoustic feature extraction is often applied to a short frame of the original signal, computing features once every 10 ms over a window of 20 or 30 ms. It is important to note that this windowing operation, assuming the acoustic feature between a frame is constant, loses acoustic properties in the window. The information loss can be minimized to the extent that humans cannot notice as long as the parameters are properly tuned for the specific application.

Pitch

Pitch is a psychoacoustical attribute of the frequency of a sound [25]. The perception of pitch makes it possible to judge sounds as "higher" and "lower" and its degree varies widely with people. Pitch detection has been instrumental in the field of psychoacoustics and audio signal processing. There are several ways to estimate the pitch, such as counting the zero-crossing rate [26] and finding the frequencies

and amplitudes of the peaks in frequency-domain [20]. A healthy young human ear can hear frequencies in the 20Hz to 20kHz range and most of the applications are configured to identify pitch within this range as accurately as possible.

Loudness

Loudness is a psychoacoustical attribute by which sounds can be ordered on a scale extending from quiet to loud. It describes the subjective perception of sound pressure [27]. One way to approximate loudness is to use the signal's root-mean-square (RMS) level in decibels. RMS is calculated by taking a series of windowed frames of the sound and computing the square root of the sum of the squares of the windowed sample values.

Timbre

Timbre is a psychoacoustical attribute by which a listener can judge that two sounds having the same loudness and pitch are dissimilar. Timbre depends primarily upon the spectrum of the stimulus, but it also depends upon the waveform, the sound pressure, the frequency location of the spectrum, and the temporal characteristics of the stimulus [28]. As such, timbre is often described using both statistical properties of the spectrum, such as spectral centroid, as well as by extracting peaks and treating the resulting frequencies as a chord, such as in roughness and inharmonicity [29].

2.2.3 Symbolic Features

Symbolic audio features are designed for a specific purpose and are dependent on application specifics. Figure 2 shows a class of popular audio features used in Music Information Retrieval research, including both acoustic and symbolic features. Take an example of the high-level features, *Score* and *Piano Roll* are essential in applications such as melody analysis but not always required for other applications such as beat detection. This is why those are classified as high-level features from the *Melodic* category.

Figure 2: Classification of features into low-level, mid-level and high-level features as suggested in [30]. Low-level features are obtained from the audio content, while high-level features are symbolic representation of music.

2.2.4 Feature Extraction in Practice

There are a number of popular open-source libraries to be used in feature extraction [31, 32, 33]. Among them, Essentia [34] is an open-source audio analysis tool that powers the similarity search functionality of Freesound. This library supports an extensive collection of reusable algorithms for audio feature extractions.

As for low-level acoustic features, Essentia supports a multitude of features such as loudness, dynamic range, zero crossing rates, as well as many spectral-based features including MFCCs, spectral energy, and pitch salience. Furthermore, many other algorithms are distinctly categorized for specific applications, such as mood detection, key detection, melody extraction, and audio fingerprinting, and each algorithm is regarded as a high-level feature extractor.

2.3 Deep Feature Learning

As introduced in the last section, traditional approaches that more or less require audio-specific domain knowledge were dominant in this field. However, recently, deep learning has seen growing popularity and success. It can replace feature engineering with automated feature learning powered by neural networks. The application of

deep learning techniques for feature extraction is known as deep feature learning or deep representation learning. In this section, we review recent advancements in machine learning research and introduce how we can utilize them to obtain audio features.

2.3.1 Neural Network

Neural networks are a computational model inspired by the biological neural networks that constitute animal brains. By training a neural network, we look for optimal parameters of the network that minimize (or maximize) an objective function. Neural networks are known to be able to powerfully model a highly non-linear relationship between input and output. At the end of the network, the model outputs a prediction. The training error is computed via an objective function, often by comparing the prediction with the target outputs, and is to be minimized.

After computing the error for an input, the network propagates the error to the entire network from back to the front. This propagation of the error is known as backpropagation. During this, the network's parameters are adjusted according to learning settings. Successive adjustments will cause the neural network to produce an output which is increasingly similar to the target output. After a sufficient number of these adjustments, the training can be terminated based on certain criteria.

2.3.2 Common Techniques in Neural Network

The optimization of neural networks is finding a local minimum of its (differentiable) objective function. Usually, it is hardly possible to find a closed-form solution of the objective function. Therefore, an optimization algorithm that finds a local minimum in an iterative way (Gradient Descent) is used. There is a variation of this type of optimization algorithms, such as Stochastic Gradient Descent, Adam [35], and AdaGrad [36].

Non-linearity is what makes neural networks powerful to learn a highly complex relationship between its input and output. Non-linearity of a network comes from

nonlinear activation functions which are often applied to an output from each layer of computation.

Previously, tanh activation and sigmoid activation $f(x) = (1 + e^{-x})^{-1}$ were the popular choice as a nonlinear activation [37, 38]. There is a study [39] that shows the nonlinear activation $f(x) = \max(0, x)$, known as Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), accelerates the training and makes it possible to explore deeper networks. The ReLU activation spurred some advanced variations such as leaky ReLU and exponential linear unit (ELU) [40]. ReLU and its variations are commonly used in audio-related tasks [41].

Having a strong non-linearity may hurt a modeling performance since the model is too closely fit to a limited set of data points (i.e., training dataset) and not well-generalized to other datasets. This modeling error is known as overfitting. Overfitting is often observed when an accuracy using a training dataset decreases steadily but the one using a validation dataset stops decreasing and starts to increase.

From an architectural perspective, a popular solution to overfitting is to add dropouts [42] after some hidden layers. Dropout is an operation that ignores the output values from a hidden layer at a certain probability (often at a rate of 30-50%). This operation is only used in the training phase but not used in the inference phase when the network makes a prediction. In the development of AlexNet (discussed later), it is reported that the introduction of dropout greatly suppressed overfitting but the time required to train the model doubled [43].

2.3.3 Convolutional Neural Network

Many successful types of neural networks differ in terms of topology structure from feed-forward network to neural networks with recurrency such as Gated Recurrent Network and LSTM.

Convolutional neural network (CNN) is one of the most widely-adopted architecture. CNN architecture was originally introduced in Neocognitron [44], which was loosely inspired by the neurological architecture of the virtual cortex. Its basic ar-

chitecture is the stack of two layers with different roles; a convolutional layer that extracts certain visual features and a pooling layer which adds rotational/positional invariance to given features.

A convolutional layer is mainly characterized by the size of its kernel (receptive field) and the number of output channels. The kernel size defines the size of the convolutional matrix, i.e., how many information a layer takes at once. On the other hand, the number of channels corresponds to how many features (a feature map) can be captured in a layer.

Many techniques and architectures that are commonly used in CNNs have been discovered since 2012, steadily advancing the performance of computer vision tasks such as ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Competition (ILSVRC). In the following sections, we discuss some important techniques and architectures regarding CNNs. Other than that, there are many alternative CNN architectures, such as GoogLeNet [45], ZFNet [46], and SENet [47].

2.3.4 AlexNet

In 2012, AlexNet [43] won the 1st position in ILSVRC, outperforming the traditional approach in object recognition which employs hand-engineered feature extraction, such as SIFT, and SVM [48] as a classifier. Today, AlexNet is known as a monumental breakthrough not only in computer vision but in machine learning in general (as of 2020, the AlexNet paper has been cited over 61,000 times).

Today, AlexNet is still used as a baseline model in different tasks. For example, researchers employed this model for sound classification tasks by using different image representations of environmental sounds, such as spectrogram and MFCC, as an input [49].

2.3.5 VGGNet

VGGNet won the 2nd position, only surpassed by the GoogLeNet, in ILSVRC 2014. The simplicity of the network architecture and the release of a pre-trained model

from the authors made it popular today as one of the choices as a baseline model for many tasks.

In the original implementation, the model takes an RGB image as input and passes the image through a stack of convolutional layers, with small kernels (filter) of size 3x3. At each layer, the outputs are followed by non-linear activation and pooling. Max-pooling is performed over a 2x2 pixel window, with stride 2. The objective of max-pooling is to down-sample an image representation, reducing its dimension and allowing for generalization of the input representation in a lower dimension.

The VGG model is specifically designed for image classification tasks, however, the architecture has also gained popularity in the audio research field. Since a spectrogram can be treated as if a 2-dimensional vector like a grayscale image, it is possible to apply the model for audio tasks with minimal modifications.

2.3.6 Classification-based Strategy

The internal representations of neural networks can be used as a feature extractor [50, 51]. For example, a neural network trained for audio tagging (classification of genre and instrument) can produce music features [52]. These classifiers must learn a certain set of important features, such as clues that identify categorical information from its input. Such features are embodied in internal representations of the network. In the case of [52], there are a few options to choose from which layer of the network to obtain the features.

2.3.7 Self-supervised Strategy

Classification-based strategy is an increasingly popular solution but it often requires strong supervision for training. To learn good representations, it requires costly annotations of huge amounts of data [53]. Self-supervised strategy has been studied to reduce the need of large labeled data by deriving labels from the significantly more unlabeled data.

How can we get a large amount of labeled data from unlabeled data? In the audio

domain, a popular approach is to utilize the correspondence between visual and audio events in videos. For example, the movement of fingers corresponds to the sound of the instrument when a piano, guitar, or drum is played; lips moving and speech when talking. By relying on such correspondence, we can use a virtually infinite amount of training resources (video) to train audio features.

Look, Listen, and Learn (L3-Net) [54] is a pioneering work in this venue. The study introduced a more human-like way of learning features, analogous to that an infant could use as their visual and audio capabilities develop. Furthermore, surprisingly, it proved that learning both audio and visual features simultaneously resulted in a significant improvement for both audio- and visual-related tasks.

More specifically to audio feature learning, [55] investigates how L3-Net design choices impact the performance of downstream audio-related tasks trained with the learned features. The study introduced a variant of the L3-Net model (OpenL3) which achieved state-of-the-art performance on popular evaluation tasks. Therefore, we use OpenL3 as a baseline model in the following experiments.

2.4 Similarity Learning

We have seen popular CNN architectures and how to use them to produce audio features. Previous approaches perform the task without a measure of similarity. It explains how probable the new input belongs to a category but ignores how similar it is to other data. In this section, we discuss another approach using similarity learning. Similarity learning is closely related to the classification approach [56], but it considers the similarity relationship among data. The notion of similarity is particularly important for data clustering. For example, we need a similarity measure when we group data in a way that looks coherent to humans.

However, despite its importance, similarity learning did not attract much attention. For example, the idea of using neural networks to extract features that respect certain relationships dates back to the 90s. Siamese Networks [57] learn to find a feature space such that similar examples have similar features and vice versa. However, it

was not feasible to train such a neural network given the limited computational power at the time [58].

Figure 3 shows an overview of similarity learning in the case of an audio-related task. There are three important steps: sampling from input data, converting the input to an embedding (feature), and computing loss using an objective function.

Figure 3: An overview of similarity learning: The first stage samples spectrograms and forms a batch. A neural network then transforms the spectrograms into features. Finally, a loss function measures the quality of our features.

2.4.1 Triplet Loss

Triplet loss is a loss function, often used in similarity learning, where an anchor input is compared to a positive input, which has the same identity with the anchor, and a negative input, which has a different identity. A triplet always consists of these three types of input, one input from each type. The distance from the anchor input to the positive input is minimized, and the distance from the anchor input to the negative input is maximized. Figure 4 visualizes this optimization.

Triplet loss has been introduced by the paper FaceNet [59]. To learn a model $f(X)$ that maps an input X to a good feature, the triplet loss L is given by

$$L = \max(D(X_A, X_P) - D(X_A, X_N) + m, 0) \quad (2.1)$$

using the Euclidean distance function

$$D(X_i, X_j) = \|f(X_i) - f(X_j)\|_2 \quad (2.2)$$

where (X_A, X_P, X_N) is a triplet of anchor, positive, and negative input and m is normally a constant value that defines the margin between positive instances and negative instances.

Figure 4: The triplet loss reduces the distance between an anchor (A) and a positive (P) and increases the distance between the anchor and a negative (N) until the separation becomes larger than the margin.

2.4.2 Triplet Mining

The way of choosing which triplets to use is essential for achieving good generalization in similarity learning [59]. The strategy to sample triplets is known as *triplet mining*. The importance of triplet mining is intuitively given in [60]. Adapting the idea to the context of sound representation learning, triplet mining is important because telling over and over again that sounds with different acoustic properties are different sounds does not teach a model anything, whereas listening to similarly-sounding but different sounds (hard negative input), or wildly different sounds of the same category (hard positive input) dramatically helps to understand the concept of “sound category”.

As mentioned in the analogy, triplets have different degrees of difficulty. For example, in Figure 5, the triplet on the top is described *easy*. The easy triplet does not produce any loss since the positive and negative input is already separated by larger than a margin. Therefore, such a triplet does not contribute to the model training and is fairly easy for the model.

On the other hand, the hard triplet is the triplet that produces the largest loss among all the combinations of the triplets. The idea to use the hardest examples is critical but it may lead to local minima early in the training [59]. To address this concern, a workaround is commonly applied, which is considered as "moderate" or "semi-hard" since it finds the hardest examples from a small batch instead of the hardest one in the dataset [60, 41].

Figure 5: The difference of the relation between positive and negative examples in easy, hard, and semi-hard triplets. (A, P, N) indicates an anchor input, a positive input, and a negative input

2.5 Clustering

The recent advancements in machine learning successfully convert a featureless audio signal into an expressive and compact representation of the acoustic information. In this section, we discuss clustering: the task of organizing the representations in a way that data in the same group (called a cluster) are more similar (in some sense) to each other than to those in other clusters. In this section, we introduce a clustering method (the k-means clustering) and an evaluation measure for clustering (rand index).

2.5.1 K-Means Clustering

Partitional clustering is a class of clustering methods that require the number of clusters to be defined before starting the process. K-means clustering is the most popular implementation of the partitional approach and it aims to partition n observations into k clusters in which each observation belongs to the cluster with the nearest means (cluster centers or cluster centroid).

Figure 6 shows a typical example of the k-means clustering result. Initially, k means are randomly selected within a dataset (in this case $k = 2$). K clusters are defined by associating each data with the nearest mean. The centroid of each of the k clusters becomes the new mean. The clustering process continues until convergence.

Figure 6: A typical example of k-means clustering result ($k = 2$).

2.5.2 Rand Index

When we have two data clusterings, e.g., a predicted one and a true one, we want to measure their similarity of the clusterings and evaluate how well the clusters are made based on the given features. Rand index [61] is a measure of the similarity between two partitions. Intuitively, it measures how much pairs of elements belong to (or not belong to) the same subject in different partitions.

For example, given a set of n elements S , suppose we have two partitions of S , $X = \{X_1, \dots, X_r\}$ which is a partition into r subjects, and $Y = \{Y_1, \dots, Y_s\}$ which is a partition into s subsets. We can define the following:

- a , the number of pairs of elements in S that are in the same subject in X and the same subject in Y
- b , the number of pairs of elements in S that are in the different subjects in X and the different subjects in Y
- c , the number of pairs of elements in S that are in the same subject in X and the different subjects in Y

- d , the number of pairs of elements in S that are in the different subjects in X and the same subject in Y

and the Rand index is

$$R = \frac{a + b}{a + b + c + d} = \frac{a + b}{{}_n C_2} \quad (2.3)$$

The shortcoming of the Rand index is that the value won't be zero even when two partitions are not correlated. A comparison with a random clustering possibly yields non-zero value. The adjusted Rand index addresses this issue by taking care of a correction for chance. Such a correction for chance establishes a baseline by using the expected similarity of all pair-wise comparisons between partitions specified by a random model [62].

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter, the methodology to perform our experiments is described. The goal of our research is to gain compact and expressive sound representations efficiently. Toward this goal, our methodology utilizes audio and text data effectively so that our neural model learns sound representations using two types of information.

Our experiment is divided into four steps. First, the data collection step starts with downloading online sound data. Second, the pre-processing step is to process the collected data and make them ready to be fed to neural networks. Third, the model training step describes the strategy and configurations of how our sound representations are optimized. Finally, the evaluation step verifies the quality of our sound representations using both subjective and objective measures.

3.1 Data collection

Our dataset is built solely based on audio data and its associated tags freely available on Freesound.org. To download efficiently from the website, we develop a script¹ which downloads sounds using the Freesound APIv2. In total, we collect 15,000 sounds. The total number of the tags associated with the sounds becomes 500. All the sounds are sampled at 16,000 Hz. Most of the sound data are often associated

¹https://github.com/kokimame/OpenFSE/blob/master/src/utils/freesound_200k_dl.py

compute 128-channel mel-scale spectrograms using an FFT window size of 64 ms with 32 ms step. We limit the power of spectrograms between -80 dB to 0 dB and then normalize it between 0 and 1. In the end, the waveform of 4 seconds is turned into a 128x128 spectrogram which is an input to our following neural network.

3.3 Model Training

3.3.1 Network Architecture

In our work, a neural network is used in the process that transforms 2-dimensional audio representations (spectrogram) to smaller 1-dimensional vectors. In order to find the right neural architecture for our purpose, we first look for an existing model that successfully performs in a similar task. We re-implement the model with minimal modifications to make it work for our task. Then, after conducting the entire experiment, we analyze the performance and see if it's possible to improve the model.

Following this strategy, we first employ the VGG-based architecture used in [63] because of its capacity to perform well in large-scale audio classification and its simplicity of implementation. Figure 8 shows the implementation detail of the model.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
Conv2d-1	[-1, 16, 128, 128]	160
MaxPool2d-2	[-1, 16, 64, 64]	0
PReLU-3	[-1, 16, 64, 64]	1
Conv2d-4	[-1, 16, 64, 64]	2,320
MaxPool2d-5	[-1, 16, 32, 32]	0
PReLU-6	[-1, 16, 32, 32]	1
Dropout-7	[-1, 16, 32, 32]	0
Conv2d-8	[-1, 16, 32, 32]	2,320
MaxPool2d-9	[-1, 16, 16, 16]	0
PReLU-10	[-1, 16, 16, 16]	1
Conv2d-11	[-1, 16, 16, 16]	2,320
MaxPool2d-12	[-1, 16, 8, 8]	0
PReLU-13	[-1, 16, 8, 8]	1
Dropout-14	[-1, 16, 8, 8]	0
Conv2d-15	[-1, 16, 8, 8]	2,320
MaxPool2d-16	[-1, 16, 4, 4]	0
PReLU-17	[-1, 16, 4, 4]	1
Conv2d-18	[-1, 16, 4, 4]	2,320
MaxPool2d-19	[-1, 16, 2, 2]	0
PReLU-20	[-1, 16, 2, 2]	1
Linear-21	[-1, 512]	32,768
BatchNorm1d-22	[-1, 512]	0

Total params: 44,534
 Trainable params: 44,534
 Non-trainable params: 0

Figure 8: The detail of our VGGish model. 2D-convolution are applied at each layer. Max-pooling follows to reduce the size of feature map while keeping the number of feature maps at 16.

3.3.2 Training Strategy

Our model is trained while updating the network’s weights by backward propagation of its prediction error (loss). The prediction error in the output layer of the network is computed based on the triplet loss function (See Section 2.4.1 for the detail of the triplet loss function).

We use plain stochastic gradient descent to optimize our model with a constant learning rate of 0.1. Our model is initially fit on a training dataset, which consists of 80% sound data, taking 80% of the instances from each of the 500 classes. In our case, the size of mini-batching is 20 because we pick 20 sound instances (4 sounds from 5 labels) and compute the triplet loss for each sound as an anchor. After every 10 epochs, we run a validation process to obtain mAP (mean average precision) scores using the latest saved models and the remaining 20% of the data.

Figure 9: Overview of the data pipeline for training. Our neural network model takes spectrograms as input which are converted from audio waveform in the pre-processing step. The model produces sound representations with about 90% smaller dimension than the original audio data.

3.3.3 Triplet Mining

The way of choosing the triplets in each mini-batch has significant effects on the speed of learning and the quality of learned representations. For our study, we compare an online semi-hard mining strategy and a hard mining strategy. As mentioned above, we choose 5 unique labels and 4 sound instances per label, forming a mini-batch of 20. Figure 10 provides a graphical explanation of our triplet mining strategy.

Figure 10: Visualization of the optimization with triplet loss. The matrix on the left shows the pair-wise feature distances that we use to find the positive and negative input for the loss computation. The circular diagram on the top right illustrates a positional relationship of the anchor, the positive, and the negative input of a triplet with a margin. The two arrows (green and red) indicate which direction does each positive and negative example need to be moved for optimization.

3.4 Adaptive Margin

Most deep metric learning algorithms, which only use coarse-grained sound classes, fail to learn distances that capture fine-grained sub-categories [64]. Such fine-grained audio similarity relationships are important to learn well-generalized acoustic features and to have a robust performance on cross-domain data (e.g., urban sound data and music instrument data).

To increase the granularity of the target sound classes, we employ the multiple tags associated with each sound data on Freesound. This expands the size of the classes, and the difference of the similarity becomes more important among the pairs of the classes. For example, the pair of tags such as 'Speech' and 'Bark' is more similar to each other than the pair of 'Horn' and 'Bark' since 'Speech' and 'Bark' are probably produced from living creatures.

We aim to consider these categorical and semantic differences among the sound classes as much as possible so that our sound representation becomes more semantically rich. We achieve this by adjusting the margin in the triplet loss formula, which was a constant value m in the equation 2.1, depending on the semantic content of the associated tags.

Figure 11 describes the idea of our adaptive margin. If two sounds are associated with semantically similar tags, no need to push two representations too much. Therefore, we apply a smaller margin than the case where two sounds are associated with semantically dissimilar tags.

Figure 11: Visualization of the desired effect of the margin adaptation. When negative and positive examples picked in a triplet are semantically similar in respect to their tags, a smaller margin should be used so that two examples can stay close, otherwise a larger margin should be applied

For mathematical formulation of adaptive margin, we look back at the equation 2.1 where the triplet loss function with a constant margin was defined. For our model

with the margin adaptation, we redefine the equation with a new term as follows,

$$L = \max(D(X_A, X_P) - D(X_A, X_N) + \alpha(A, P, N), 0) \quad (3.1)$$

where $\alpha(A, P, N)$ denotes the adaptive margin that takes the tags associated with the anchor, positive, and negative (A, P, N) as input.

Following [64], we define our adaptive margin $\alpha(A, P, N)$ as follows,

$$\alpha(A, P, N) = \beta + d_{semantic}(t_A, t_N) \quad (3.2)$$

where $d_{semantic}(t_A, t_N)$ computes the semantic similarity distance between two sets of the associated tags (t_A, t_N). β is the constant margin term which guarantees that even for two very similar sets of the tags, their margin is certainly larger than zero. In this way, the model correctly learns from the difference between the examples which are semantically similar but acoustically dissimilar (negative). Furthermore, our sound representations are L2 normalized, no margin larger than 4 is possible.

We define the semantic similarity of two sets of the tags as,

$$d_{semantic}(t_A, t_N) = \frac{\|g(t_A) - g(t_N)\|^2}{4 - \beta} \quad (3.3)$$

where $g(t_A)$ is the semantic embedding of the tags t_A . The Euclidean distance between two semantic embedding ranges from 0 to 2 since $g(\cdot)$ is L2 normalized. The term $4 - \beta$ is applied to make the adaptive margin lie in the range $[0, 4]$

The semantic embedding of a set of tags is computed simply by averaging the word vectors of each tags in a set as follows,

$$g(t_A) = \frac{\sum_i w_i}{\|\sum_i w_i\|_2} \quad (3.4)$$

where w_i is the i -th word vector of a tag in the set of tags. To obtain a word vector, we use Spacy² and base the word representation on `en_core_web_md` dataset.

3.5 Evaluation

We evaluate our sound representation using both objective and subjective measures. MFCCs and the features produced by the OpenL3 model are used as a baseline in the evaluation. For objective evaluation, the sound representations are tested in two tasks; a discriminative task and a clustering task. We experiment with a well-known open dataset ESC50 [65] for both tasks. ESC50 consists of 2000 audio clips of duration 5 sec, labeled with one of 50 environmental sound classes, such as glass breaking, car horn, and wind.

3.5.1 Discriminative Task

In a discriminative task, we first extract features from audio clips using four different models (ours with margin adaptation, ours without margin adaptation, OpenL3, and MFCCs). Then, we train a multi-layer perceptron to predict ESC50 categories based on the features. The accuracy of this classification is the final score of the performance in this task. The accuracy is computed by taking an average of 5-fold cross-validation as those are recommended by the original creator of the dataset.

3.5.2 Clustering Task

In a clustering task, the features which are previously extracted using four different models are directly clustered using k -means clustering, setting $k = 50$. Then, we obtain the score of this clustering task by computing Adjusted Rand Index between the predicted clustering and the true clustering (the true labels of the given dataset)

²<https://spacy.io/usage/vectors-similarity>

3.5.3 Subjective Task

For a subjective task, we developed a simple interactive website (Figure 12) in which a user can see the clustering of sound data and listen to each sound by placing the cursor on a data point. In this way, the user can evaluate the sound clustering based on our sound representations by subjectively examining if a cluster of sounds has any coherent characteristics (e.g., in respect to acoustic properties or semantics of the associated tags). Visualization of the clustering is made possible by using dimension reduction methods, such as Principle Component Analysis or t-SNE, to project high-dimensional features to 2D/3D space.

Figure 12: This is a screenshot of an open-source web application we developed for subjective evaluation. In the middle of the screen, users interact with sound data clustering which is constructed with our sound representations. Users can rotate the clustering in 2D/3D space and the original sound data will be played when the cursor hovers over its data point in the clustering. In the left panel, users choose the dataset for clustering and the methods of dimension reduction. From the search box in the right panel, users search data points with a specific label and corresponding points will be highlighted in the clustering.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

4.1 Choice of Triplet Mining Strategy

We tested two triplet mining strategies, semi-hard mining and hard mining for our similarity learning. Figure 13 shows how the average distance between positive and negative examples in triplets changes as the model training continues.

Figure 13: The transition of average distance between positive (blue) and negative (red) examples. Left: semi-hard mining, Right: hard mining.

4.1.1 Discussion

With semi-hard mining, the left figure clearly illustrates the sound representations are successfully optimized using the triplet loss. Namely, while negative examples (red) are closer to anchor than positive ones (blue) on average at the beginning, the negatives are pushed far away and the positive comes closer as the training

continues. At 1000 epochs, the average distance is flipped. Even when positives are being closer than negatives, the optimization can progress due to the margin term.

On the other hand, the right figure shows the hard-mining strategy failed to optimize the representations. The average distances of both positive and negative examples do not almost change.

We assume this error can be attributed to some exceptional data. Since we solely rely on the user-generated and user-labeled audio data from Freesound.org, it is probable to include some data that are wrongly labeled or have some exceptional acoustic properties (e.g., too loud). Why did not this cause trouble in semi-hard mining? This is, we hypothesize, because the hard-mining more likely choose such exceptional data as negative or positive since the hard-mining always look for an example that results in the largest loss.

Note that the negative inputs are closer to the anchor at the beginning in both cases. This is reasonable because, in triplet mining, we pick closer ones as negative and farther ones as positive so that the loss function produces a meaningful amount of loss value. Therefore, considering all the representations (whether it is negative or positive) are initially distributed randomly, negative representations are likely farther than positive ones on average.

4.2 Discriminative Task Result

We evaluate how well our sound representations perform in a supervised and discriminative task, i.e., classification (See Section 3.5.1). It is found that the representations with the adaptive margin (MA) work better than the one without it (WOMA), making a 6% difference in the accuracy in the discriminative task. Second, the MA representation results in the score as good as MFCCs but the OpenL3-based feature outcores the rest of the features by a large margin. Table 1 shows the average accuracy of the 5-fold cross-validation.

Model	MA	WOMA	OpenL3	MFCCs
Accuracy	45%	39%	77%	46%

Table 1: Results of our discriminative task. OpenL3-based feature outcores two our models and MFCC baseline largely.

4.2.1 Discussion

Comparing with the result of OpenL3, our best model loses by a large margin in the discriminative task. This is probably because we could not use as much data as used in OpenL3 because of the lack of GPU memory. OpenL3 uses more than about 200K sound events obtained from videos during training while we only use 15K short audio files.

The shortage in the GPU memory becomes a problem partly because of the way our system loads the training samples. With appropriate modifications in the system, it would be possible to use much more training data from Freesound without running out of the GPU memory.

4.3 Clustering Task Result

Next, we evaluate our sound representations in a clustering task (See Section 3.5.2), measuring the Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) between a predicted clustering and the true clustering. The three approaches based on neural networks (MA, WOMA, and OpenL3) attain almost equally high scores, achieving about 3 times higher than MFCCs.

Model	MA	WOMA	OpenL3	MFCCs
ARI	0.137	0.134	0.164	0.046

Table 2: The scores of the Adjusted Rand Index in the clustering task.

4.3.1 Discussion

The performance of our two models is almost equal to OpenL3. This is remarkable because our models achieve state-of-the-art performance with fairly a limited amount

of data, as explained above. This result suggests that similarity learning is highly powerful to learn sound representations for the purpose of clustering tasks.

4.4 Subjective Evaluation

We visualize our sound representations to evaluate the quality of the data clusterings subjectively. We use t-SNE [66] for dimensionality reduction in order to project the high-dimensional sound representations in a 3D space. The learning rate for t-SNE is set to 10, and the perplexity is to 12. The label importance factor [67] is disabled. It is found 700 iterations are needed for t-SNE to converge in all the four representations.

4.4.1 Discussion

In Figure 14, you can observe that both of our models (a, b) produce a number of clusters of sound representations. Clusters having dots with the same color show sound representations with the same acoustic category are grouped together. Since the ESC50 dataset consists of 40 sound examples for 50 categories, each cluster ideally has 40 members with the same color. This is most clearly invalidated in the plot (d) because there are too many too small clusters that have about 5 to 10 members. Also, in the plot (c), the clustering is almost shrunk to 2-dimension. In fact, the OpenL3 representation is quite unsuitable and became entirely flat in some trials (t-SNE is non-deterministic, and it produces different results each time).

In addition, our visualization tool facilitates the subjective evaluation greatly. It allows users to rotate/scale the clustering and directly listen to the sounds represented by dots.

Figure 14: T-SNE visualization of sound representations produced by the four models; (a) MA, (b) WOMA, (c) OpenL3, (d) MFCC. Visualization is made with our interactive tool²

4.5 Conclusions

In this work, we investigated how suitable similarity learning is to train deep sound representations for the purpose of data clustering. Our experiments revealed that our sound representations trained in similarity learning achieved the performance on a par with the state-of-the-art model in a clustering task, even we use a limited amount of training data. However, the state-of-the-art model outscored our model by a large margin in the discriminative task. In conclusion, our results showed that similarity learning is a viable choice to train sound representations for clustering, but more work is required to make it work well for discriminative tasks.

In future work, we challenge the issue of the discriminative task by training with a larger training dataset. For this purpose, we need to rebuild our data-loading scheme so that it can handle a larger dataset without running out of GPU memory. In addition, the credibility of the evaluation needs to improve by testing with other datasets with different acoustic categories. In this work, we only used the ESC50 dataset which focuses on environmental sounds. However, since our training dataset consists of many music-related sounds (See Figure 7), we are interested to confirm that our sound representations possibly perform better in more music-related evaluations, such as genre classification [68].

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